

ACTION citizen science impact assessment canvas

Key problem you want to address	Key research question
<p>What social, economic, environmental problem are you trying to (contribute) to solve?</p> <p><i>Example: Air pollution, especially that is generated by private mobility, in Turin (Italy)</i></p>	<p>What is the main research question addressed by your CS project?</p> <p><i>Example: how does private mobility traffic impact on air quality in specific areas of the city and on specific moments of the day?</i></p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Key stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers <i>Representing which disciplines? Junior or senior?</i> • Citizen scientists <i>Do you foresee engaging any specific social group? Is your project working towards inclusiveness? What is the gender distribution in your group of citizens: female/male/not disclosed/other?</i> • Policy/decision makers <i>Are you targeting local/national or international policy/decision makers?</i> • Business actors <i>Will your project provide input to business actors? Are you collaborating with business actors as part of your project?</i> • Other organisations <i>Will you collaborate with other organisations? What kind of organisation can benefit from the project's activities/results?</i> • General public <i>Do you foresee reaching local, national or international audiences?</i> 	

<p>Input</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where are you starting from? • What was there before the beginning of the project? • What are the economic/technical and human resources you will use besides the one provided by ACTION? How much do they cost? <p><i>Example: this project is the continuation of a previous one, we already have 200 CS engaged and 5 lead researchers</i></p>	<p>Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What will you do? • What do you do to engage your stakeholders? <p><i>Example: Air quality monitoring with low cost DIY sensors. 5 events. 3 training workshops</i></p>
<p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the tangible results you expect to deliver? • How many people do you aim to engage? • How many people do you aim to reach through communication? • How many policy makers? <p><i>Example: a new version of our air quality measurement sensor; a curated dataset; 3 publications. 500 CS engaged. 1k reached</i></p>	<p>Short-terms and long-term impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What positive change do you expect for your stakeholders? • Which areas of impact are more relevant? (see ACTION impact assessment framework in the next page and described in the PPT attached) • Which dimensions are more relevant? (see ACTION impact assessment framework in the next page and described in the PPT attached) <p><i>Example: citizens will be more aware of air quality, better informed on how to reduce exposure, 10% will change their moving behaviours. Policy makers will change mobility policies. Papers deeply up taken by researchers in the field.</i></p>

**Assign a value from 1 to 5 to each areas of impact and to the related dimensions
(1 is not relevant/we do not aspect impacts. - 5 is very relevant/will be a crucial impact)**

Definitions of the areas of impact and related dimensions are in the PPT that accompany this canvas

	Value
Scientific impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Scientific knowledge	
New research fields and interdisciplinarity	
New knowledge resources	
Innovation in education	

	Value
Political impact	<i>Medium or media value</i>
Impact on policy process	
Political participation	
Self-governance	
Political support for citizen science	

	Value
Social impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Community building and empowerment	
Social inclusion	
Researchers and research community's growth and empowerment	
Knowledge, skills and competences	
Changes in way of thinking, attitude and values	
Behavioural change	

	Value
Economic impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Impact on employment	
Cost saving	
Income and revenue generation for leading organisations	
Economic impact on the local communities	

	Value
Other impacts	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Please specify.....	
Please specify.....	

	Value
Environmental	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Impact on ecosystem	
Impact on biodiversity	
Impact on soil quality	
Impact on water quality	
Impact on air quality	
Impact on health	

